

BMD

Biodiversity Meets Data

Guidelines on how to manually enter metadata into the LifeWatch ERIC BMD Data Catalogue

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About the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue

The LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue (<https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu>) adopts a subset of the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) version 2.2.0 standard to describe its dataset metadata records. The schema includes 77 metadata elements.

Here below we describe in detail the main sections and some of the corresponding metadata fields to provide a basic guideline to correctly fill in the BMD dataset metadata records.

Basic Information

Publication Date	<i>The date when the resource was or will be made publicly available in the format DD.MM.YYYY.</i>
Title	<i>The title of the dataset. For example, for the Bioclim+ dataset in CHELSA the title could be 'CHELSA Bioclim+'.</i>
Short Name	<i>The short name of the dataset. For example, for the Bioclim+ dataset in CHELSA the title could be 'Bioclim+'. This is optional.</i>
Abstract	<i>A brief overview of the resource that is being documented. The abstract should include basic information that summarises the resource.</i>
Dataset Language	<i>The language of the dataset.</i>
Keyword	<i>The keyword associated with the dataset. Keywords must be entered one by one and not all together, separated with a comma, otherwise the search and discoverability can be negatively affected.</i>
Keyword Thesaurus	<i>The name of the official keyword thesaurus from which the keyword was derived. The keyword thesauri are usually discipline specific. You can put "none" if no thesaurus is used (in case of free keywords).</i>

Contact Information

Dataset Creator	<p><i>The name, surname, organisation name, position, email, and user ID of the person that contributed to creating the dataset. To know the creator, check the "License and Attribution" section or the publication associated with the dataset or data source.</i></p> <p><i>For the Organisation Name, report only the name of the organisation without the address and country (e.g., Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL).</i></p> <p><i>Under 'User id', if available, add the ORCID ID of the creator (full link).</i></p>
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Metadata Provider *The name, surname, organisation name, position, email, and user ID of the person that created the documentation for the resource. This means that if metadata is not available publicly and you are the one compiling the metadata fields by collecting information coming from different sources, you are the metadata provider.*

Associated Party *This is the party associated with the dataset. This section is optional and can be skipped if the Dataset Creator is present.*

Dataset Contact *The name, surname, organisation name, position, email, and user ID of the person who should be contacted about the dataset.*

Distribution *The link(s) associated with the dataset (e.g., download link, DOI, S3 bucket, etc).*

Geographic Information

Geographic Description *The geographic description of the dataset (e.g., Global, Europe, Italy, Spain, Germany, etc).*

Bounding Coordinates *The North, South, East, and West Bounding Box Coordinates, as well as the Minimum and Maximum altitude. Make sure that the values are integers (e.g., -180 and not -179.9888).*

Temporal Information

Temporal Coverage *The start and end date covered by the dataset. If you have only the years, please use the first month for the begin date and the last month for the end date. For example, for a temporal range 1981 - 2100, use '01/01/1981 - 31/12/2100'.*

NOTE: watch out for the date format, because depending on the dataset it can be displayed as MM.DD.YYYY rather than DD.MM.YYYY.

Taxonomic Information

Taxonomic Coverage *The taxonomic information about the species reported in the dataset. Make sure that what is reported is in line with the NCBI Taxonomy. If the dataset is about abiotic data, you can leave this section empty.*

Licence Information

- Intellectual Rights** *The intellectual property rights regarding the usage and licensing of the dataset. You can modify the following standard sentence according to the needs: This data package is released to the public domain under Creative Commons CC0 1.0 - No Rights Reserved.*
- Licence Name** *The official licence name associated with the dataset. The name should match the name of a well-known license from the SPDX license vocabulary or a similar persistent vocabulary (e.g., Creative Commons, CC-BY-4.0, etc.)*
- License URL** *The persistent URL for the license, typically a SPDX URL, or an official URL from another well-known license vocabulary (e.g., if licence is CC0 1.0, the URL is <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>).*
- Acknowledgement** *Report here one or more sentences that acknowledge funders and other key contributors to the study (excluding the dataset authors listed in the creator field).*

Project Information

The project section is not mandatory, but in general it contains information on the project in which this dataset was collected. It is optional, but when the user decides to specify it, all mandatory metadata have to be inserted.

- Title** *The title of the project*
- Abstract** *The abstract of the project*
- Personnel** *The name, surname, organisation name, and position of the person involved in the project.*

Methods Information

The methods section is not mandatory, but in general it contains information on the methods used to generate the dataset. It is optional, but when the user decides to specify it, all mandatory metadata have to be inserted.

- Description** *The description of the methods used to generate the data. In the 'Citation' section, report the main publication associated with the dataset.*
- Instrumentation** *The description of the instruments used to generate the dataset.*
- Software** *The title of the software with its version. In case of a dataset, report the latest version of the dataset.*

Sampling *The description of the study extent and sampling strategy used to generate the dataset.*

Data Table Information

Name *The name in which the dataset can be identified. For example, dataset_version1.csv.*

Format Name *The dataset format (e.g., GeoTIFF, CSV, Sqlite).*

Attribute List *The variables/layers present in the dataset. Try to be as comprehensive and detailed as possible regarding the variable name ('Name'), the variable label, the variable definition, and the standard unit used to report the variable.*
The 'Name' is the official name of the attribute (e.g., pH, salinity, air temperature, etc). This is often a short, sometimes cryptic name (for example, in CHELSA, for air surface temperature, the variable name is 'tas'). This often represents the name of the variable that is found in the header of a data file.
The 'Label' is the descriptive label that can be used to display the name of an attribute. This is often a longer, possibly multiple word name for the attribute with respect to the attributeName. For example, an attribute with a name 'spcode' might have a label 'Species Code'.
The 'Definition' is the precise definition of attribute in the data entity being documented. It explains the contents of the attribute fully so that a data user could interpret the attribute accurately.
The 'Standard Unit' is the unit assigned to the variable (e.g., for temperature is °C, for pressure is Pascal, etc).

Missing Value Code *The code used in the dataset to identify missing values.*

Measurement Scale *The type of scale from which values are drawn for the attribute. It can be non-numeric and numeric.*

Annotation *The persistent URI used to identify a property from a vocabulary.*